

A NOVEL DOMESTIC NON-BIO WASTE (LOW-DENSITY POLYETHYLENE AND POLYPROPYLENE) MANAGEMENT SYSTEM USING MYCOREMEDIATION

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to address the environmental threat posed by persistent plastic pollution. It focused on the biodegradation potential of low-density polyethylene (LDPE) and polypropylene by soil fungi. Plastic samples were sterilized, weighed, and incubated with fungal isolates obtained from plastic-contaminated soil. Four dominant fungal strains were identified using lactophenol cotton blue staining. Two degradation methods were used: plastic incubation in nutrient broth with fungal isolates under shaking conditions, and embedding plastics in soil under static conditions, both for 60 days. Enzymatic assays detected laccase, esterase, and protease—enzymes known to aid in plastic degradation. Weight loss of plastic samples was recorded at 30, 45, and 60-day intervals, showing consistent degradation. Among the four isolates, two demonstrated significantly higher degradation and enzyme activity. Identified through ITS sequencing as *Aspergillus tamaraii* and *Aspergillus flavus*, these strains showed strong enzymatic responses. SEM and FTIR analyses confirmed biodegradation by revealing surface erosion, cracking, and changes in chemical bonds of the plastic. The study concludes that *A. flavus* and *A. tamaraii* effectively degrade LDPE and polypropylene, transforming them into simpler forms more efficiently than other isolates tested.

Key words: *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus tamaraii*, low-density polyethylene, Mycoremediation, Polystyrene, Polypropylene, Polyvinylchloride

INTRODUCTION

The term "plastic" is derived from the Greek word *plastikos*, meaning "capable of being shaped or molded" (Fried, 1995). Plastics are synthetic polymers primarily composed of carbon, hydrogen, oxygen, silicon, and nitrogen, with crude oil, natural gas, and coal as their primary raw materials. Due to their high durability and versatility, plastics have become indispensable in modern life (Strong *et al.*, 2006). Common types include polyethylene (PE), polypropylene (PP), polyvinyl chloride (PVC), polyethylene terephthalate (PET), polystyrene (PS), polyurethane (PUR), and various nylons. However, their chemical resistance and non-biodegradable nature contribute to persistent environmental pollution, with degradation taking several decades (Srikanth *et al.*, 2022). Plastic waste disrupts soil ecology by forming an impermeable layer, impeding air and water infiltration, thus reducing soil fertility and groundwater recharge. Its hydrophobic, high-molecular-weight polymeric structure contributes to resistance against microbial degradation (Wilkes *et al.*, 2017).

Types of Plastics

Plastics are broadly categorized into thermoplastics and thermosets. Thermoplastics, such as LDPE and PP, are recyclable and can be remelted. In contrast, thermosets possess irreversible cross linked molecular structures, making them non-recyclable (Chan Ji, 1999; Albano *et al.*, 2009; Choi *et al.*, 2009; Al-Salem *et al.*, 2010; Barbuta *et al.*, 2010; Mohammadian & Haghi, 2013). PE and PP are the most widely used plastics, comprising approximately 29.6% and 18.9% of global plastic consumption, respectively (Wu *et al.*, 2017; Yang *et al.*, 2018). PE is a simple ethylene-based polymer, while PP, a heat- and chemical-resistant polyolefin, contains a methyl group that further enhances its resistance to microbial attack (Khoironi *et al.*, 2019; Alshehrei, 2017).

Environmental Impact of Plastic Waste

Plastic pollution leads to severe ecological consequences. It has been associated with immune dysfunction, endocrine disruption, and carcinogenicity in both terrestrial and aquatic organisms (Pavani & Rajeswari, 2014; Munir *et al.*, 2018). Hazardous additives such as heavy metals, dyes, and plasticizers leach into ecosystems, contaminating soil and water bodies. Approximately 80%

of marine plastic waste originates from land-based sources (Sheavly, 2005; Alabi *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, drifting plastics facilitate the transport of invasive species (Derraik, 2002; Hasnat & Rahman, 2018). Incineration of plastic releases toxic gases like CO and HCN, contributing to air pollution (Purwaningrum, 2016).

Plastic Waste Management and Degradation Strategies

Traditional waste management techniques—recycling, incineration, and landfilling—have significant limitations in cost, efficiency, and environmental safety (Al-Salem *et al.*, 2009; Hopewell *et al.*, 2009; Gan & Zhang, 2019). Alternative strategies include photo-, chemical, thermal, and gamma-ray degradation, which are energy-intensive and ecologically disruptive (Ojha *et al.*, 2017; Pramila & Ramesh, 2011). Consequently, microbial biodegradation has emerged as a sustainable and eco-friendly solution (Soundararajan, 2021).

Biodegradation of Plastic Polymers

Biodegradation involves microbial enzymes breaking down polymers into simpler molecules, such as oligomers and monomers, which are then assimilated into microbial metabolic pathways (Gu, 2003; Agrawal & Singh, 2016). Biofilm formation enhances microbial adhesion and enzymatic action. The process involves bio deterioration, depolymerization, assimilation, and mineralization (Muhonja *et al.*, 2018; Bikiaris, 2013). Over 400 plastic-degrading bacterial species have been identified (Lear *et al.*, 2021).

Fungal Bioremediation (Mycoremediation)

Fungi are efficient bioremediation agents due to their adaptability and rapid mycelia growth, enabling them to colonize and degrade various substrates, including plastics (Kim & Rhee, 2003; Nandi & Joshi, 2013). Fungi thrive in diverse and even extreme environments, making them ideal for environmental cleanup efforts.

Fungal Enzymes in Plastic Biodegradation

Enzymes like laccases, peroxidases, and lipases play vital roles in fungal-mediated plastic degradation:

- **Laccases (EC 1.10.3.2)** are multicopper oxidases that degrade phenolic and non-phenolic polymers using oxygen as an electron acceptor (Bilal *et al.*, 2016; Giardina *et al.*, 2010). They are widely distributed among fungi, especially white-rot fungi (Thurston, 1999).
- **Peroxidases (EC 1.11.1)** include lignin peroxidase, manganese peroxidase, and versatile peroxidase. These heme-containing enzymes catalyze oxidation reactions critical to lignin and plastic degradation (Conesa *et al.*, 2002).
- **Lipases (EC 3.1.1.3)** hydrolyze ester bonds in lipids, enabling degradation of fatty waste and potential breakdown of plastic components (Sharma *et al.*, 2001; Masse *et al.*, 2001).

Analytical Techniques: SEM and FTIR

- **Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)** offers high-resolution imaging to visualize surface degradation on plastics at nanometer scales, confirming microbial or enzymatic activity.
- **Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy** identifies changes in chemical bonds of polymers, providing insight into the breakdown of functional groups during degradation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The following materials were used in this study: soil samples, plastic samples—Low-Density Polyethylene (LDPE; hand cover and bin cover), Polypropylene (PP; straw), Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), Czapek Dox Agar (CDA), nutrient broth, distilled water, conical flasks, Petri plates, and test tubes.

Sample Collection

Soil Samples

Two soil samples were collected from known plastic waste accumulation sites in the Bannerghatta region: Vajpayee Circle and Laxmipura. Soil was collected from a depth of 0–15 cm using sterile techniques to minimize external contamination. Approximately 500 g of soil was collected at each

site, transferred into sterile zip-lock covers while wearing gloves, and labeled according to the collection site—‘V’ for Vajpayee Circle and ‘L’ for Laxmipura.

Plastic Samples

Two types of plastics were selected: LDPE (hand cover and bin cover) and PP (straw). LDPE samples were cut into 3×3 cm squares, and PP into 1.5×1.5 cm squares. Each sample was weighed prior to treatment.

Isolation of Fungi

Fungal isolates were obtained from the collected soil samples using the serial dilution technique (10^{-1} to 10^{-7}). One gram of each soil sample was suspended in 10 ml of sterile distilled water and subjected to serial dilution. Aliquots were plated on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) using the pour plate method. Plates with dilutions 10^{-3} to 10^{-5} showed distinct fungal colonies and were sub-cultured on Czapek Dox Agar (CDA) to obtain pure cultures. The resulting master plates were preserved for subsequent experimentation.

Fungal Characterization

Macroscopic and Microscopic Observation

The fungal isolates were characterized based on macroscopic colony features (color, texture, morphology) and microscopic features using lactophenol cotton blue staining. A compound microscope was used to examine hyphal structures and spore morphology. Four dominant fungal strains were selected—two from the 10^{-3} dilution and two from the 10^{-5} dilution—for further analysis.

Pre-Treatment of Plastic Samples

All plastic pieces were sterilized by autoclaving at 121°C for 20 minutes. After sterilization, each sample was reweighed to monitor any subsequent mass changes during degradation experiments.

Incubation of Plastic Samples with Fungal Isolates

(a) Soil-Based Petri Plate Assay

A thin layer of sterilized soil from each site was added to separate Petri plates. Autoclaved plastic pieces were placed onto this soil layer, then covered with another layer of the same soil. The plates were inoculated with respective fungal isolates and incubated at 37°C. Fungal inoculation was repeated every 3–4 days. Each plate was labeled according to the soil origin and fungal strain.

(b) Nutrient Broth-Based Conical Flask Assay

Twelve conical flasks were filled with nutrient broth, and each received a single plastic sample. Each flask was inoculated with a specific fungal isolate and incubated at 37°C in a shaker incubator for 60 days. Nutrient broth was replenished every 3 days. All flasks were appropriately labeled.

Enzyme Profiling of Fungal Isolates

Laccase Assay

Laccase activity was detected spectrophotometrically using ABTS (2,2'-azino-bis(3-ethylbenzothiazoline-6-sulfonic acid)) as a substrate.

Esterase Assay

Esterase activity was determined using α -naphthol. Briefly, 4.0 ml of standard α -naphthol solution was mixed with 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) to make up 5.0 ml, followed by the addition of 1.0 mL of DBLS. Absorbance was measured at 600 nm.

Protease Assay

Protease activity was assessed via agar well diffusion. Agar media containing 1% casein, skimmed milk, and gelatin was poured into Petri plates. After solidification, 3 mm wells were made, and culture supernatants were loaded into the wells. Plates were incubated at 37°C overnight and observed for clear zones indicating proteolytic activity.

Physicochemical Analysis of Degraded Plastics

A. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Surface topography of treated plastic samples was examined using SEM. To improve electron conductivity and imaging resolution, samples were sputter-coated with gold using a low-vacuum sputter coater. Coated samples were mounted on aluminum stubs using conductive double-sided tape, introduced into the SEM chamber, and visualized using secondary electron detection.

B. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

FTIR analysis was performed to identify structural and functional group changes in plastic polymers post fungal treatment. Spectra were recorded using the IR Prestige-21 model. Changes in peak intensities and shifts were analyzed to confirm chemical modification or degradation of polymers.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

COLLECTION OF SOIL SAMPLES: Two different soil samples were collected from different waste disposable sites of Bannerghatta (Vajpayee circle and Laxmipura). The soil was collected from the plow layer. i.e., from 0-15 cm. About 100g of soil was collected and packed in sterilized zip covers. The covers containing soil samples were named according to the location from where they have been collected.

Figure 2. (A) Collection of soil sample from Vajpayee circle, (B) Collection of soil sample from Laxmipura, (C) Collected soil samples packed in sterilized zip covers.

ISOLATION OF FUNGI:

The soil fungi were isolated by the serial dilution method. One gram of the soil sample was suspended in 10 ml of sterile distilled water to make serial dilutions (10^{-1} to 10^{-7}). One mL of each dilution was placed on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) and incubated for 48 hours at 37°C .

Figure 3. Serial dilution of the collected soil samples.

MACROSCOPIC AND MICROSCOPIC OBSERVATION OF ISOLATED FUNGI:

The isolated fungi were sub-cultured by the streak plate method and the obtained pure cultures were observed under a microscope by lactophenol cotton blue staining.

Figure 4. (A) $L-10^{-3}$ Black: Strain grown in the soil collected from Laxmipura in the 3rd dilution, (B) $L-10^{-5}$ White: Strain grown in the soil collected from Laxmipura in the 5th dilution, (C) $V-10^{-3}$ Green: Strain grown in the soil collected from Vajpayee Circle in the 3rd dilution, (D) $V-10^{-3}$ Black: Strain grown in the soil collected from Vajpayee Circle in the 3rd dilution.

GROWTH OF FUNGAL MYCELIUM IN THE CONICAL FLASKS CONTAINING PLASTIC SAMPLES:

Figure 5. (A) Conical flasks containing nutrient broth and the selected plastics, inoculated with fungal strains on day-1, (B) Growth of fungal mycelium in the flasks after 15 days of inoculation.

MEASUREMENT OF WEIGHT OF SAMPLES AT AN INTERVAL OF 15, 30, 45 AND 60 DAYS:

WEIGHT OF PLASTIC SAMPLES PLACED IN CONICAL FLASKS (g)

Table 1. The weight of plastic samples was placed in the conical flasks at an interval of 1, 15, 30, 45, and 60 days respectively. The weight of plastic sample (Thick cover) placed with V-10⁻³ Green was reduced significantly compared to other strains.

	1 st day	15 th day	30 th day	45 th day	60 th day
V-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	0.026	0.024	0.023	0.020	0.019
V-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	0.026	0.022	0.021	0.020	0.019
V-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	0.086	0.086	0.079	0.076	0.075
V-10 ⁻³ Green Straw	0.026	0.022	0.019	0.017	0.017
V-10 ⁻³ Green Hand cover	0.026	0.023	0.019	0.019	0.017
V-10 ⁻³ Green Thick cover	0.086	0.086	0.079	0.071	0.071
L-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	0.026	0.022	0.021	0.020	0.019
L-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	0.026	0.022	0.021	0.020	0.018
L-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	0.086	0.086	0.079	0.079	0.076
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Straw	0.026	0.021	0.020	0.020	0.016
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Hand cover	0.026	0.026	0.023	0.020	0.014
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Thick cover	0.086	0.086	0.081	0.079	0.076

Graph 1. Measurement of weight loss of Polypropylene (straw), and LDPE (hand cover, thick cover) at an interval of 1,15,30,45, and 60 days.

WEIGHT OF PLASTICS SAMPLES KEPT IN PETRIPLATES WITH SOIL (g)

	1 st day	60 th day
V-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	0.026	0.023
V-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	0.026	0.023
V-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	0.086	0.062
V-10 ⁻³ Green Straw	0.026	0.023
V-10 ⁻³ Green Hand cover	0.026	0.022
V-10 ⁻³ Green Thick cover	0.086	0.072
L-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	0.026	0.017
L-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	0.026	0.023
L-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	0.086	0.068
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Straw	0.026	0.023
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Hand cover	0.026	0.023
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Thick cover	0.086	0.072

Table 2. The weight of plastic samples placed in the Petri plates on the 1st and 60th day. The weight of plastic sample (Thick cover-LDPE) placed with V-10⁻³ Black was reduced significantly compared to other strains.

Graph 2: Measurement of weight loss of Polypropylene (straw), and LDPE (hand cover, thick cover) on 1st and 60th day.

ENZYME ACTIVITIES:**ESTERASE ACTIVITY (u/ml)**

	30 DAYS	45 DAYS	60 DAYS
V-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	63.93	24.88	113.74
V-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	52.32	28.43	127.96
V-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	49.76	17.77	135.07
V-10 ⁻³ Green Straw	49.76	17.77	234.60
V-10 ⁻³ Green Hand cover	49.76	21.32	135.07
V-10 ⁻³ Green Thick cover	60.42	10.66	156.40
L-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	36,87	31.99	170.62
L-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	53.32	28.43	110.19
L-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	42.65	21.32	188.39
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Straw	53.32	28.43	163.51
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Hand cover	67.53	39.10	170.62
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Thick cover	31.99	21.32	120.85

Table 3. Determination of esterase activity in an interval of 30, 45, and 60 days of incubation. The enzymes in the strain V-10⁻³ Green were found to show the highest activity on the 60th day compared to other strains.

Graph 3. Determination of esterase activity (u/ml) in the strains V-10⁻³ Black, V-10⁻³ Green, L-10⁻³ Black, L-10⁻⁵ White on 30th day, 45th day, and 60th day of incubation.

LACCASE ACTIVITY (u/ml)

	30 DAYS	45 DAYS	60 DAYS
V-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	0.0132	0.013	0.025
V-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	0.0082	0.029	0.060
V-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	0.0060	0.018	0.040
V-10 ⁻³ Green Straw	0.0071	0.049	0.068
V-10 ⁻³ Green Hand cover	0.0091	0.028	0.045
V-10 ⁻³ Green Thick cover	0.0060	0.035	0.059
L-10 ⁻³ Black Straw	0.0067	0.017	0.036
L-10 ⁻³ Black Hand cover	0.0117	0.041	0.052

L-10 ⁻³ Black Thick cover	0.0110	0.039	0.051
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Straw	0.0058	0.033	0.053
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Hand cover	0.0115	0.025	0.025
L-10 ⁻⁵ White Thick cover	0.0043	0.022	0.036

Table 4. Determination of laccase activity in an interval of 30, 45, and 60 days of incubation. The enzymes in the strain V-10⁻³ Green were found to show the highest activity on the 60th day compared to other strains.

Graph 4. Determination of laccase activity in the strains V-10⁻³ Black, V-10⁻³ Green, L-10⁻³ Black, and L-10⁻⁵ White on the 30th day, 45th day, and 60th day of incubation.

PROTEASE ACTIVITY

Figure 6. Agar plates showing protease activity. (A) Control, (B) V-10⁻³ Green hand cover, (C) V-10⁻³ Green straw, (D) V-10⁻³ Green thick cover, (E) L-10⁻³ Black hand cover, (F) L-10⁻³ Black straw, (G) L-10⁻³ Black thick cover, (H) V-10⁻³ Black hand cover, (I) V-10⁻³ Black straw, (J) V-10⁻³ Black thick cover, (K) L-10⁻⁵ White hand cover, (L) L-10⁻⁵ White straw, (M) L-10⁻⁵ White thick cover.

MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF FUNGAL CULTURE USING ITS1 AND ITS4 PRIMER

Molecular Identification of Sample L-1

Phylogenetic Tree:

The evolutionary history was inferred using the Neighbor-Joining method [Saitou N *et al.* 1987]. The optimal tree is shown. The percentage of replicate trees in which the associated taxa clustered together in the bootstrap test (500 replicates) are shown below the branches (above the branches) [Felsenstein J. *et al.*, 1985]. The evolutionary distances were computed using the Kimura 2-parameter method [Kimura M. *et al.*, 1980] and are in the units of the number of base substitutions per site. The rate variation among sites was modeled with a gamma distribution (shape parameter = 2). This analysis involved 11 nucleotide sequences. Codon positions included were 1st+2nd+3rd+Noncoding. All positions containing gaps and missing data were eliminated (complete deletion option). There was a total of 549 positions in the final dataset. Evolutionary analyses were conducted in MEGA11 [Tamura K.*et al.*, 2021].

Figure 7. Evolutionary analysis by Maximum Likelihood method

Interpretation of result:

Sample labeled as **L-10⁻⁵ White** showed high similarity with *Aspergillus tamarii*, based on nucleotide homology and phylogenetic analysis.

MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF SAMPLE 2

PHYLOGENETIC TREE:

Figure 8. Evolutionary analysis by Maximum Likelihood method

Interpretation of result:

The sample labeled as **V- 10⁻³ Green** showed high similarity with *Aspergillus flavus*, based on nucleotide homology and phylogenetic analysis.

SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE

Gold sputtering: Plastic samples effectually dissipate charge when bombarded with electrons, this causes imaging artifacts. After fixing of samples, they were coated with a thin layer of a conductive metal to minimize damage to samples that improved topographical contrast for improved imaging by SEM using secondary electron detection. Low vacuum system grade of sputter coat unit was used. Gold sputtering was used for visualizing image. Sample was fixed to stub using conductive double sided tape. Top of the vaccum chamber was removed and stub was placed in the center of platform of vaccum chamber. Top of the vaccum chamber was replaced. Gas leak knob was closed by turning clockwise. Pump was turned on using power strip on floor, control box was turned on.

Gold Sputter coater was turned on and plugged into back of the control box. Counter on sputter coater was set to 30seconds. When vacuum reached 3×10^{-1} mbars, the 'ON' light on the sputter coater was switched on. Test button on sputter coater was pushed and held on. Gas leak knob was opened counter clockwise until current reached 20-25 mA. Test button was left and start button was pushed on control box. After 30 seconds, the coater automatically stopped, turn off the sputter coater, the control box, and the pump. The vacuum was released by slowly lifting the bleeder valve on top of the vacuum chamber. Stub was removed, proper coating was observed by pale brown coating on the specimen. The stub was put into the sample holder and tightened with an allen wrench. The sample holder was put into the larger holder being sure to match up the slot and tightened with an Allan wrench. The plastic sample was now ready to SEM imaging.

Figure 9. Scanning Electron Microscopic view of degraded LDPE (hand cover and thick cover) and Polypropylene sheets. (A) Polypropylene control, (B) Polypropylene sheet placed with *Aspergillus tamarii*, (C) Polypropylene sheet placed with *Aspergillus niger*, (D) LDPE-hand cover sheet control, (E) LDPE-hand cover sheet placed with *Aspergillus tamarii*, (F) LDPE-hand cover

Table 9. IR Spectrum values of the peaks obtained from the graph

POLYPROPYLENE-(STRAW) CONTROL	V-10 ⁻³ BLACK	L-10 ⁻⁵ WHITE	L-10 ⁻³ BLACK	V-10 ⁻³ GREEN	VIBRATIONS
3393.75	3400.41	3300.11	3399.48	3361.64	Amines N-H stretch
2949.67	2951.04	2950.94	2950.58	2950.12	Alkanes C-H stretch
2867.42	2867.84	2837.32	2867.61	2867.62	Aldehydes C-H stretch
2917.22	2917.87	2918.13	2917.77	2918.09	Aldehydes C-H stretch
2838.45	2838.24	2838.45	2838.09	2838.34	Aldehydes C-H stretch
1577.71	1645.46	1647.32	1643.76	1579.09	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
1454.63	1453.14	1451.52	1453.10	1454.55	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
1375.52	1375.78	1375.71	1375.75	1375.72	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
841.02	840.74	840.54	840.73	840.96	Alkyl & Aryl Halides

FTIR spectroscopy data of LDPE (HAND COVER)

Graph 6. FTIR Spectroscopy data of LDPE (HAND COVER). A-Control, B-Treated with the strain V-10⁻³ Black, C- Treated with the strain L-10⁻⁵ White, D-Treated with the strain L-10⁻³ Black, E- Treated with the strain V-10⁻³ Green

LDPE-(HANDCOVER) CONTROL	V-10 -3 BLACK	L-10-5 WHITE	L-10 ⁻³ BLACK	V-10 ⁻³ GREEN	VIBRATIONS
3394.37	3389.09			3348.59	Amines N-H stretch
2915.00	2915.00	2915.37	2915.66	2915.22	Alkanes C-H stretch
2917.43		2848.00	2848.65		Alkanes C-H stretch

2867.43	2847.73	1471.91		2847.98	Alkanes C-H stretch
2838.43		1017.81		1723.82	Carboxylic Acids O-H stretch
1578.95	1644.60		1471.76	1608.03	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
1454.63	1471.90		1462.38	1471.95	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
1375.60	1462.06		1019.03	1462.21	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
841.04	875.14	875.17	875.13	875.16	Alkyl & Aryl Halides

Table 10. IR Spectrum values of the peaks obtained from the graph

Graph 7. FTIR Spectroscopy data of LDPE (THICK COVER). A-Control, B-Treated with the strain V-10⁻³ Black, C- Treated with the strain L-10⁻⁵ White, D-Treated with the strain L-10⁻³ Black, E- Treated with the strain V-10⁻³ Green.

LDPE-(THICK COVER) CONTROL	V-10⁻³ BLACK	L-10⁻⁵ WHITE	L-10⁻³ BLACK	V-10⁻³ GREEN	VIBRATIONS
3396.14	3375.48	3299.36	–	3382.15	Amines N–H stretch
2915.63	2915.84	29815.7	2915.71	2915.84	Alkanes C–H stretch
2848.07	2848.01	2848.04	2848.00	2848.05	Carboxylic Acids O–H stretch
1596.14	1472.21	1472.08	1472.18	1643.07	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
1653.57	1651.63	1462.52	–	1472.17	Alkenes C=C stretch
1462.80	1462.54	1378.08	1462.57	1462.58	Nitro Compounds NO ₂ stretch
792.92	730.07	730.10	730.07	730.07	Alkyl & Aryl Halides C–Cl stretch
719.01	719.12	719.06	719.11	719.12	Alkyl & Aryl Halides C–Cl stretch

Table 11. IR Spectrum values of the peaks obtained from the graph for LDPE-(THICK COVER) Control.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The soil was collected from the major plastic dumpsites in and around Bannerghatta, Bangalore, Karnataka state. The soil fungi were isolated by serial dilution technique using Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) by pour plate method. 2 types of plastics were selected to study the ability of fungal species in degradation. i.e., low-density polyethylene and polypropylene since they have been widely used in our daily lives. The selected plastics were inoculated with isolated fungal species and incubated for 60 days in 2 different ways. One of the ways was in the petri plates along with the soil and the other way was in the conical flasks containing the essential nutrients required by the fungi for their growth. The weight of all the plastics was measured at an interval of 1,15,30,45, and 60 days. Along with the weight of plastics, different enzyme activity by fungi was also

measured at an interval of 30, 45, and 60 days. Finally, after a period of incubation of 60 days, the plastic samples treated with fungal species were observed under Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and FTIR Spectroscopy for analysis of degradation.

One of the biggest environmental issues of the present is plastic disposal because a significant amount of synthetic plastic is still not biodegradable. Many researchers have proved that many microbes have the ability to degrade plastic polymers. Microbes have the ability to break down the plastic polymer under the right conditions of all the microbes, it has been found that fungi can break down these polymers very easily since they can produce many enzymes. The capacity of various fungal species can cause chemical and physical changes in various plastic polymers

In this plastic biodegradation, fungi play a pivotal role, they act on plastics by secreting some degrading enzymes i.e., laccase, esterase, and proteases, and the presence of some pro-oxidant ions can cause effective degradation. Different strains of fungi were isolated, Characterization of fungi was done using Lactophenol Cotton Blue staining, and identification of isolated fungi was done using Molecular Identification of fungal Culture using ITS1 and ITS4 Primer in our study. By this technique, 2 different species of fungi were identified namely, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Aspergillus tamaritii* The plastic sheets that were treated with these fungi were analysed using a scanning electron microscope and FTIR Spectroscopy which evidently proved the ability of isolated fungi to degrade the selected plastic sheets.

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